

XIOS TUTORIAL

```

...
CHARACTER(*) pfilename
INTEGER,INTENT(IN) :: pim,pjm
REAL,DIMENSION(pim,pjm),INTENT(IN) ::
INTEGER,INTENT(IN) :: par_orix, par_sz.
INTEGER,INTENT(IN) :: pitau0
REAL,INTENT(IN) :: pdate0, pdeltat
INTEGER,INTENT(OUT) :: pfileid, phoriic
.
INCLUDE "netcdf.inc"

INTEGER :: ncid, iret
INTEGER :: leng, lengf, lenga
CHARACTER(LEN=120) :: file, tfile
INTEGER*30 :: timenow

```


Context : Earth system models

✚ Complex coupled model, long simulations, a lot of data generated...

✚ Example for past CMIP5 exercise

- 167 numerical experiments, 25000 simulated years (20th and 21th century, last millennium, paleo-climate).
- Monthly, daily and high frequency (6h) files
 - Up to 800 variables for each files
 - A lot of metadata associated to each variable
- 5 Millions generated files
- 2 PB of data

+ CMIP6 next exercise

- Beginning mid-2016
- x 7 => 14 PB of data to be generated, stored and distributed (ESGF grid)

3 main challenges for climate data production

+ Efficient management of data and metadata definition from models

- Human cost, errors...

+ Efficient production of data on supercomputer parallel file system (HPC)

- 1 file by MPI process ?
 - Rebuild files
- Parallel I/O efficiency ?

+ Complexity and efficiency of post-treatment chain to be suitable for distribution and analysis

- Files rebuild, time series, seasonal means...
- Mesh regridding, interpolation, compression...
- Resiliency ?

More time is spent to output and post-treat data than running the simulation !

XIOS is addressing all these challenges

+ Flexibility in management of I/O and data definition

- Using an external XML file parsed at runtime

+ I/O Performance issue

- Dedicated Parallel and Asynchronous I/O server

+ Post-treatment issue

- Integrate internal parallel workflow and dataflow
- Post-treatment can be performed "In Situ"

XIOS is a ~5 years old software development

+ XIOS 2.0 : ~ 85 000 code lines, written in C++, interfaced with Fortran models

- Open Source CECILL Licence
- Code versioning : SVN (subversion)
 - XIOS 2.0 (dev) : `forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/ioserver/svn/XIOS/trunk`
 - XIOS 1.0 : `forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/ioserver/svn/XIOS/branches/xios-1.0`

+ Used by an increasing variety of models

- IPSL models : NEMO, LMDZ, ORCHIDEE, INCA, DYNAMICO
- LGGE (MAR), Ifremer (ROMS, MARS3D)
- European NEMO consortium
- MétéoFrance / CNRM (ongoing) : Gelato, Surfec, Arpège climat (CMIP6 production)
- European models (in evaluation) : MetOffice (Hadgem ? , MONC, Gung-Ho?), ECMWF (Open IFS ?, EC-EARTH ?)

+ Web site : wiki page

- <http://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/ioserver/wiki>
- Ticket system management and sources browsing : TRAC
- Documentation : on wiki page and under SVN (doc/ directory)
 - Reference guide : [xios_reference_guide.pdf](#)
 - User guide : [xios_user_guide.pdf](#)
- Support mailing list : subscribe yourself
 - XIOS users list (users support) : xios-users@forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr
 - XIOS developers list : xios-dev@forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr
 - XIOS team (non public) : xios-team@forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr

+ XIOS Team

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- Arnaud Caubel (CEA/LSCE - IPSL)
- Manh Ha Nguyen (LSCE)
- Remy Lacroix (ex-LSCE, CNRS/IDRIS)
- Julien Derouillat (CEA/MdS)

Philosophy:

+ Each time step, models expose part of their data through a minimalist interface

- Identifier (ASCII string) + address (pointer) of the data

➤ Output:

```
CALL xios_send_field("field_id", field_out)
```

➤ Input:

```
CALL xios_recv_field("field_id", field_in)
```

+ External XML File :

- Describe the incoming data flow from models using XML attributes
- Describe the workflow applied to the incoming data flow
- Describe the data flow end point => output to files or returned to model

+ Simplicity and Flexibility

- XML file is parsed at runtime
 - Metadata, workflow and output definition can be modified without recompiling
- Hierarchical approach using strong inheritance concept
 - Attributes are inherited from parent to child
 - Avoiding redundant definition, simple and compact
 - Very useful when you need to describe hundred's of variables

+ Full interactivity with models through the XIOS Fortran API

- All XML definitions can be completed or created from model

✦ Output a variable in a "hello_word" file like an averaging at 1 day frequency

- Define 1D-Axis and horizontal 2D-domain associated with the model variables

```
<domain id="horizontal_domain" ni_glo="100" nj_glo="100"/>  
<axis id="vertical_axis" n_glo="100" />
```

- Define grid associated with the associated axis and domains

- ✦ Example 3D grid : 100x100x100

```
<grid id="grid_3d">  
  <domain domain_ref="horizontal_domain"/>  
  <axis axis_ref="vertical_axis"/>  
</grid>
```

- Define fields (variables) associated with the grid

```
<field id="a_field" grid_ref="grid_3d">
```

- Associate fields with files

```
<file name="hello_word" output_freq="1day">  
  <field field_ref="a_field" operation="average">  
</file >
```

```
<xios>
  <context id="hello_word" >

    <axis_definition>
      <axis id="vertical_axis" n_glo="100" />
    </axis_definition>

    <domain_definition>
      <domain id="horizontal_domain" ni_glo="100" nj_glo="100" />
    </domain_definition>

    <grid_definition>
      <grid id="grid_3d">
        < domain domain_ref="horizontal_domain" >
          < axis axis_ref="vertical_axis" >
        </grid_definition>

    <field_definition >
      <field id="a_field" operation="average" grid_ref="grid_3d" />
    </field_definition>

    <file_definition type="one_file" output_freq="1d" enabled=".TRUE.">
      <file id="output" name="hello_world" output_freq="1d">
        <field field_ref="a_field" />
      </file>
    </file_definition>

  </context>
</xios>
```

```
SUBROUTINE client(rank,size)
  USE xios
  IMPLICIT NONE
  INTEGER :: rank, size, ts
  TYPE(xios_time)      :: dtime
  DOUBLE PRECISION,ALLOCATABLE :: lon(:,,:),lat(:,,:),a_field (:,:)
  ! other variable declaration and initialisation .....

! XIOS initialization
  CALL xios_initialize("client", return_comm=comm)
  CALL xios_context_initialize("hello_word",comm)
! Complete horizontal domain definition
  CALL xios_set_domain_attr("horizontal_domain",ibegin=ibegin,ni=ni,jbegin=jbegin, nj=nj)
  CALL xios_set_domain_attr("horizontal_domain ",lonvalue_2d=lon, latvalue_2d=lat)
! Setting time step
  dtime%second=3600
  CALL xios_set_timestep(dtime)
! Closing definition
  CALL xios_close_context_definition()
! Entering time loop
  DO ts=1,96
    CALL xios_update_calendar(ts)
    CALL xios_send_field("a_field",a_field)
  ENDDO
! XIOS finalization
  CALL xios_context_finalize()
  CALL xios_finalize()
END SUBROUTINE client
```

XML : Extensible Markup Language

- Set of rules to define a documents in a format
- Both human-readable and machine readable

+ Tag : a markup construct that's begin by "<" and ends by ">"

- Start-tag : `<field>`
- End-tag : `</field>`

+ Element : construct delimited by a start-tag and an end-tag

- May be empty : `<field></field>`
 - Can be written with empty-tag syntax : `<field />`

- May have child elements

```
<field_group>
```

```
  <field />
```

```
  <field />
```

```
</field_group>
```

- May have content : text between start-tag and end-tag element

```
<field> content </field>
```

- Only use in XIOS to define arithmetic's operations

+ **Attributes** : a construct composed of a pair : `name="value"` defined into a start-tag or an empty tag element

- Ex : Element field has 3 attributes : `id`, `name` and `unit`
- `<field id="temp" name="temperature" unit="K" />`

+ **Comments** : delimited by starting tag comment `<!--` and ending tag comment `-->`

- `<field> <!-- this is a comment, not a child nor a content --> </field>`

+ **XML document must be well-formed**

- XML document must contains only one root element
- All start-tag element must have the matching end-tag element (case sensitive) and reciprocally
- All element must be correctly nested

+ XML master file must be `iodef.xml`

- Parsed first at XIOS initialization
- Root element name is free
- Root element can only contain `<context>` type elements.

+ 5 main element families: represent objects type stored into XIOS database

- `context` : isolate and confine models definition, avoiding interference between them
- `field` : define incoming field from model
- `axis` : define 1D-axis
- `domain` : define 2D-domain
- `grid` : define multi-dimensional grid, composed of axis and domains
- `file` : define input or output file
- `variable` : define parameters for models or for XIOS parameterization

+ These families can be declined into 3 flavors (except for context elements)

- Simple elements : ex : `<field />`
- Group elements : ex : `<field_group />`
 - ✦ Can contains children simple element
 - ✦ Can contains children nested group of the same type
- Definition elements : ex : `<field_definition>`
 - ✦ Unique root element type
 - ✦ Act as a group element, ie can contains other groups or simple elements

✚ Each element may have several attributes

✚ ie : `<file id="out" name="output" output_freq="1d" />`

- Attributes give information for the related element
- Some attributes are mandatory, so error is generated without assigned value (small part)
- Some other are optional but have a default value
- Some other are completely optional

✚ Attributes values are ASCII string and, depending of the attribute, can represent :

- A character string : ex: `name="temperature"`
- An integer or floating value : ex : `output_level="3" add_offset="273.15"`
- A boolean : true/false : ex : `enabled="true"`
 - ✚ Fortran notation `.TRUE./FALSE.` are allowed but obsolete
- A date or duration : ex : `start_date="2000-01-01 12:00:00"`
 - ✚ See format later
- A bound array (inf,sup) [values] : ex : `value="(0,11) [1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12]"`

✦ Special attribute `id` : identifier of the element

- Used to take a reference to the corresponding element
- Is unique for a kind of element
 - ✦ Same id for different elements refers internally to the same object
 - ✦ Be very careful when reusing same ids, not advised
 - ✦ Root elements are equivalent to group elements with a fixed id
 - ✦ Ex: `<field_definition ...>` ⇔ `<field_group id="field_definition" ...>`
- Is optional, but no reference to the corresponding element can be done later

✦ XML file can be split in different parts.

- Very useful to preserve model independency, i.e. for coupled model
- Using attribute "`src`" in context, group or definition element
 - ✦ attribute value give the name of the file to be inserted in the database

File iodef.xml :

```
<context src="./nemo_def.xml" />
```

file nemo def.xml :

```
<context id="nemo" >  
  <field_definition ... >  
  ...  
</context>
```

Why Inheritance ?

- Attributes can be inherited from an other element of same family
- Hierarchical approach, very compact
- Avoiding useless redundancy

+ Inheritance by grouping : parent-children inheritance concept

- All children inherit attributes from their parent.
- An attribute defined in a child is not inherited from his parent.
- Special attribute "id" is never inherited

```
<field_definition level="1" prec="4" operation="average" enabled=".TRUE.">
  <field_group id="grid_W" domain_ref="grid_W">
    <field_group axis_ref="depthw">
      <field id="woce"          long_name="vertical velocity"          unit="m/s" />
      <field id="woce_eff"     long_name="effective ocean vertical velocity" unit="m/s" />
    </field_group>
  </field_group>
</field_definition>

==>  <field id="woce" long_name="vertical velocity" unit="m/s" axis_ref="depthw"
      domain_ref="grid_W" level="1" prec="4" operation="average" enabled="true" />
```

+ Inheritance by reference

- Only for field, domain and axis elements
 - `field` => `field_ref` attribute
 - `domain` => `domain_ref` attribute
 - `axis` => `axis_ref` attribute
- Source element inherit all attributes of referenced element
 - Attributes already defined in source element are not inherited

```
<field id="toce" long_name="temperature" unit="degC" grid_ref="Grid_T" enabled="true" />
```

```
<field id="toce_K" field_ref="toce" long_name="temperature (K)" unit="degK" />
```



```
<field id="toce_K" long_name="temperature (K)" unit="degK" grid_ref="Grid_T" enabled="true"/>
```

- Warning, reference inheritance is done **AFTER** group inheritance
 - Be careful with potential side effects
- Reference may have additional meaning
 - Ex : `field_ref` bind also the data value of the referenced field
 - See later in tutorial matching section

Why Context ?

- Context is similar to a "namespace"
- Context are isolated from each other, no interference is possible
 - Ids can be reused with no side effects between context
- For parallelism, each context is associated with its own MPI communicator
 - No interference between MPI communication
- Generally a context is associated to one model
 - Principle of modularity
- A model can declare more than one context

+ Context element : `<context/>`

- Can appear only as a child element of the root XML element
- Must have an id
- Can contains only calendar or other element root definition

```
<context id="nemo" />
  <calendar />
  <field_definition> ... </field_definition>
  <file_definition> ... </file_definition>
  <axis_definition> ... </axis_definition>
  <domain_definition> ... </domain_definition>
  <grid_definition> ... </grid_definition>
  <variable_definition> ... </variable_definition>
</context />
```

+ Each context must define an associate calendar

- One calendar by context
- Define a calendar type
 - Date and duration operation are defined with respect to the calendar
- Define starting date of the model
- Define time step of the model

+ Calendar type

- **Gregorian** : standard Gregorian calendar
- **D360** : fixed 360 days calendar
- **NoLeap** : fixed 365 days calendar
- **AllLeap** : fixed 366 days calendar
- **Julian** : Julian calendar
- **user_defined** : months and days can be defined by user (planetology and paleoclimate)

+ Date and Duration

- A lot of XML attributes are of date or duration type
- Operation between date and duration are strongly dependent of the chosen calendar
 - Ex : date + 1 month = date + 30 day only for month 4,6,9,11

+ Duration units

- Year : `y`
- Month : `mo`
- Day : `d`
- Hour : `h`
- Minute : `mi`
- Second : `s`
- Time step : `ts` (related to time step context definition)

+ Duration format

- Value of unit may be integer or floating (not recommended), mixed unit may be used in a duration definition
 - Ex. : `"1mo2d1.5h30s"`
 - Ex. : `"5ts"`

+ Date format

- `year-month-day hour:min:sec`
 - Ex. : `"2015-12-15 10:15:00"`
- Partial definition are allowed taking taking into account rightmost part
 - Ex. `"2015-12"` equivalent to `"2015-12-01 00:00:00"`

- Date can be also define with a duration offset
 - Useful for defining a calendar based on standard units (seconds for example)
 - Ex. : "+3600s"
 - Or mixt : "2012-15 +3600s" equivalent to "2012-15-1 01:00:00"

+ Specific attribute calendar

- **type** : define the calendar type
 - "Gregorian", "D360", "NoLeap", "AllLeap", "Julian" or "user_defined"
- (date) **time_origin** : define the simulation starting date (fixed at "0000-01-01" by default)
- (date) **start_date** : define the starting date of the run (fixed at "0000-01-01" by default)
- (duration) **timestep** : define the time step of the model : mandatory

+ Setting calendar

- From XML : specific child context element : calendar

```
<context id="nemo" />  
  <calendar type="Gregorian" time_origin="2000-01-01" start_date="2015-12" timestep="1h"/>  
  ...  
</context />
```

+ Defining an user define calendar

- ◊ Planetology or paleo-climate can not use standard calendar
- ◊ Personalized calendar
 - ✦ Defining `day_length` in second (default 86400)
 - ✦ Defining `month_lengths` : number of days for each 12 months
 - ✦ Or if you don't want to specify month : `year_lenght` in second : months would be equally distributed

```
<calendar type="user_defined" day_length="86400"  
          month_lengths="(1,12) [31 28 31 30 31 30 31 31 30 31 30 31]" />
```

- ◊ Possibility to define leap year
 - ✦ Attributes : `leap_year_month`, `leap_year_drift`, `leap_year_drift_offset`
 - ✦ See documentation...

Managing calendar, date and duration from Fortran interface

✚ Duration

- Fortran derived type : `TYPE(xios_duration)`
 - ✦ Component (`REAL`): `year, month, day, hour, minute, second, timestep`
 - ✦ Predefined constant : `xios_year, xios_month, xios_day, xios_hour, xios_minute, xios_second`

```
TYPE(xios_duration) :: duration
duration%second = 3600.
Duration = 3600 * xios_second
```

✚ Date

- Fortran derived type : `TYPE(xios_date)`
 - ✦ Component (`INTEGER`): `year, month, day, hour, minute, second`

```
TYPE(xios_date) :: date(2014,12,15,10,15,0)
date%year=2015
```

✚ Date and duration operation

- Duration operation: `duration±duration, duration*real, -duration, comparison : ==, /=`
- Date operation : `date - date`, boolean operators : `==, >=, >, <=, <, /=`
- Date and duration operation : `date+duration, date-duration`
- String conversion : `xios_duration_convert_[to/from]_string,`
`xios_date_convert_[to/from]_string`
- Useful functions : `xios_date_get_second_of_year, xios_date_get_day_of_year,`
`xios_date_get_fraction_of_year, xios_date_get_fraction_of_day`

+ Setting calendar from Fortran interface

- Within single call

```
SUBROUTINE xios_define_calendar(type, timestep, start_date, time_origin)  
  CHARACTER(LEN=*) :: type  
  TYPE(xios_duration) :: timestep  
  TYPE(xios_date) :: start_date, time_origin
```

- Or with individual call

```
SUBROUTINE xios_set_timestep(timestep)
```

```
SUBROUTINE xios_set_time_origin(time_origin)
```

```
SUBROUTINE xios_set_start_date(start_date)
```

+ Field geometry is provided by the underlying mesh description

- Describe field dimensionality (1D, 2D, 3D or more)
- Describe field topology (rectilinear, curvilinear, unstructured)
- Describe field data distribution for parallelism

Describing the mesh : the grid element : `<grid />`

- Can describe element of any dimension : 0D (scalar), 1D, 2D, 3D, or more.
- Defined by composition of 1D-axis and 2D-horizontal domain
 - `axis` and `domain` elements
- Empty grid is representing a scalar

```
<grid_definition />
  <grid id="grid_3d" <!-- grid 3D of dimension 100x50x20 -->
    <axis n_glo="100"/>
    <axis n_glo="50"/>
    <axis n_glo="20">
  </grid >

  <grid id="grid_4d" <!-- grid 4D of dimension 100x100x50x20 -->
    <domain ni_glo="100" nj_glo="100" type="rectilinear"/>
    <axis n_glo="50"/>
    <axis n_glo="20">
  </grid >
</ grid_definition />
```

Axis description : the axis element <axis />

- Describe 1D axis, generally vertical axis

✚ Defining the global size of the axis

- (integer) `n_glo` attribute

✚ Defining the data parallelism distribution across MPI processes

- (integer) `n` attribute
 - Local axis size distribution
- (integer) `begin` attribute
 - Local axis distribution beginning with respect to the global axis
 - Follow C-convention, starting from 0.
- If nothing specified, the axis is considered as not distributed.

✚ Defining axis coordinate values and boundaries

- (real 1D-array) attribute : `value [n]`
- (real 2D-array) attribute : `bounds [2, n]`

✚ Defining how data are stored in memory

- Data are stored in memory as Fortran array
- But data can be masked, or ghost cells are not valid data, or axis value can be compressed
- XIOS will extract only required value from memory
- Must describe valid data with attributes
- Default is : whole data are valid

✚ Masking Data (optional)

- (boolean 1D-array) `mask` attribute : `mask[n]`
- Masked data will not be extracted from memory and will appear as missing values in output files

✚ Defining ghost cells (optional)

- (integer) `data_n` attribute
 - Size of the data in memory (default : `data_n=n`)
- Integer attribute : `data_begin`
 - Offset with respect to local axis distribution beginning (default : `data_begin=0`)
 - Negative offset : data outside of the local distribution will not be extracted (ghost cell)
 - Positive offset : data in interval `[begin, data_begin]` and/or `[data_begin+data_n-1, begin+n-1]` are considered as masked.

+ Defining compressed data

- Data can be compressed in memory (ex : land point), but may be decompressed to be output
- Undefined data are considered as masked and will be output as missing value
- (integer 1D-array) `data_index` attribute : `data_index[data_n]`
 - Define the mapping between data in memory and the corresponding index into the local axis distribution
 - `data_index[i]=0` map the beginning of the local distribution
 - Negative index or greater than `n-1` will be outside of the distribution and will not be extracted

+ Other attributes

- (string) `name`
- (string) `long_name`
- (string) `unit`
- (bool) `positive` : set "positive" CF attribute in Netcdf output

+ Using distributed axis within grid

- Global 3D-grid of size 100x50x20
- Describe a local 3D distribution of size 10x5x20 beginning at the index (20,10,0) of the global grid

```
<grid id="grid_3d">  <!-- grid 3D of global dimension 100x50x20 -->
  <axis n_glo="100" begin="20" n="10" />
  <axis n_glo="50"  begin="10" n="5"  />
  <axis n_glo="20">  <!-- not distributed -->
</grid >
```

- Data distribution is different for each MPI process, not suitable for XML description
 - Attributes only known at run-time can be passed dynamically using the Fortran interface
 - See section Fortran interface setting attributes

+ Masking grid point individually

- In the last example, masking one point in the 3rd axis means masking a full 2D layer in the 3d grid
- Grid point can be masked using the mask attribute
- Regarding of the dimensionality of mask arrays, version mask_1d to mask_7d are allowed
 - Total mask size must be equal to the local domain size
 - Ex : `<grid id="grid_3d" mask_3d="(10,5,20) [...,..., ...]">`
 - or `<grid id="grid_3d" mask_1d="(1000) [...,..., ...]">`

2D horizontal layer description : the domain element <domain />

- Describe generally 2D layers mapping the surface of the sphere
- Large variety of 2D domains can be described
- (string) **type** attribute :
 - "rectilinear", "curvilinear" or "unstructured"

- Regular Cartesian
(longitude x latitude)

- Curvilinear

- Reduced Gaussian

- Unstructured

✚ Rectilinear or curvilinear domains have a 2D description

- (integer) ni_glo, nj_glo : global domain size for each direction (longitude and latitude for rectilinear)
- (integer) $ibegin, ni, jbegin, nj$: local domain definition

✦ Data representation in memory : similar to 1D-axis but for 2 dimensions

- Can be 1D-array (horizontal layer as a vector) or 2D-array
 - ✦ (integer) `data_dim` attribute : 1 or 2
- (integer) `data_ni` : size of the first array dimension (default : `data_ni=ni`)
- (integer) `data_ibegin` attribute : Offset for the first dimension with respect to local domain distribution beginning : may be negative or positive (default : `data_ibegin=0`)
- [if `data_dim=2`] `data_nj`, `data_jbegin` : 2nd dimension (default: `data_nj=nj`, `data_jbegin=0`)
- Example for `data_dim=2`, negative offsets to eliminate ghost cells

- Example for `data_dim=1` : horizontal layer seen as a point vector
 - Positive offsets, local domain from different processes can overlap

1D data in memory : `data_dim = 1`

+ Unstructured domain have a 1D description

- Vector of cells
 - `ni_glo`, `ni` and `ibegin` can be specified
 - `nj_glo`, `nj` and `jbegin` are meaningful
- Data in memory is always a vector
 - `data_dim=1`

+ Compressed data (i.e land use)

- For `data_dim=1` (==decompressed data is a 1D-array)
 - `data_i_index[data_ni]` : index for decompressed local domain represented by vector (exclusive with `data_ibegin`)
- For `data_dim=2` (==decompressed data is a 2D-array)
 - `data_nj` must be equal to `data_ni`
 - `data_i_index[data_ni]`, `data_j_index[data_ni]` : indexes for decompressed local domain represented as a 2D-array (exclusive with `data_ibegin`, `data_jbegin`)

+ Masking data

- (boolean 1D-array) `mask_1d` attribute : 1d array version
 - `mask_1d[ni*nj]` for rectilinear and curvilinear domain
 - `mask_1d[ni]` for unstructured
- (boolean 2D-array) `mask_2d` attribute : 2d array version
 - `mask_2d[ni,nj]` for rectilinear and curvilinear domain only

✚ Defining coordinates

- ◆ For rectilinear domain
 - `latvalue_1d[ni]` : latitude coordinates
 - `lonvalue_1d[nj]` : longitude coordinates
- ◆ For curvilinear
 - `latvalue_2d[ni,nj]` : latitude coordinates
 - `lonvalue_2d[ni,nj]` : longitude coordinates
 - `bounds_lat_2d[4,ni,nj]` : latitudes boundaries
 - `bounds_lon_2d[4,ni,nj]` : longitudes boundaries
- ◆ For unstructured domain
 - (integer) `nvertex` : max corners/edges of cells
 - (double) `latvalue_1d[ni]` : latitude coordinates
 - (double) `lonvalue_1d[ni]` : longitude coordinates
 - (double) `bounds_lat_2d[nvertex,ni]` : corners latitude coordinates
 - (double) `bounds_lon_2d[nvertex,ni]` : corners longitude coordinates
 - If cell nb corners < `nvertex`, corners must be cyclic redundant (CF compliance)

The field element `<field />`

✦ Represent incoming or outgoing data flux from models

✦ Data can be sent or received at each time step from model through the Fortran interface

- Sending data

```
CALL xios_send_field("field_id", field)
```

- Receiving data

```
CALL xios_recv_field("field_id", field)
```

✦ Fields geometry and parallel distribution is hosted by the underlying grid description

- (string) `grid_ref` attribute : id of the grid

- For more flexibility fields can refer to a domain

- ✦ (string) `domain_ref` attributes => create a virtual 2D grid composed of the referred domain

- Or a domain and an axis to create a virtual 3D grid

- ✦ `domain_ref` and `axis_ref`

```
<grid id="grid_3d">
  <domain id="domain_2d/">
    <axis id="axis_1d" />
  </domain>
</grid>
...
<field id="temp" grid_ref="grid_3d"/>
```

~

```
<axis id="axis_1d" />
<domain id="domain_2d/">
...
<field id="temp" domain_ref="domain_2d"
          axis_ref="axis_1d"/>
```

+ Data fields from models must be conform to the grid description

- Fields can be declared of any dimensions in single or double precision
- But total size and data order must be the same than declared in the grid
 - Example :

```

<grid id="grid_3d">
  <domain id="domain_2d" type="rectilinear" ni_glo="100" ni="10" data_ni="14"
                                             nj_glo="50"  nj="5"  data_nj="7"/>
  <axis id="axis_1d" n_glo="20"/>
</grid>
...
<field id="temp" grid_ref="grid_3d"/>

```

- Global grid : 100x50x20
- Local grid : 10x5x20
- Data in model memory : $(data_ni \times data_nj \times n_glo) = (14 \times 7 \times 20) = 1960$
- Can be declared as :
 - REAL(kind=4) :: temp(14,7,20)
- Or REAL(kind=4) :: temp(1960) but data order must be (14,7,20) following the row major order Fortran convention
- Or REAL(kind=8) :: temp(1960)

+ Field can be output to files

- Will appear as a child file element
- Construct files by including list of field required
- A field can appear, in more than one file
 - using the reference attribute : `field_ref`

```
<field_definition>
  <field id="temp"      grid_ref="grid_3d"/>
  <field id="precip"   grid_ref="grid_3d"/>
  <field id="pressure" domain_ref="domain_2d"/>
</field_definition>

<file_definition>
  <file name="daily_output" freq_output="1d">
    <field field_ref="temp" />
    <field field_ref="pressure" />
  </file>

  <file name="monthly_output" freq_output="1mo">
    <field field_ref="temp" />
    <field field_ref="precip" />
  </file>
</file_definition>
```

+ Field attributes related to file output

◊ Field description :

- (string) **name** : name of the field in the file. If not specified, "id" will be used in place
- (string) **long_name** : set "long_name" netcdf attribute conforming to CF compliance
- (string) **standard_name** : set "standard_name" netcdf attribute
- (string) **unit** : set "unit" netcdf attribute
- (double) **valid_min/valid_max** : fix valid_min & valid_max netcdf attribute

◊ Enable/disable field output

- (boolean) **enabled** : if **false**, field will not be output (default=**true**)
- (integer) **level** : fix the level of output of the field (default=0) with respect to "level_output" file attribute if (**level**>**level_output**) the field will not be output

◊ Setting missing values : fix masked point value in output file

- (double) **default_value** : if not set, masked point value will be undefined

◊ Setting precision / compression

- (integer) **prec** : define the output precision of the field : 8 -> double, 4->single, 2-> 2 byte integer
- (double) **add_offset**, **scale_factor** : output will be (field+**add_offset**)/**scale_factor**, usefull combine with **prec=2**
- (integer) **compression_level** (0-9) : fix the gzip compression level provided by netcdf4/hdf5: due to HDF5 limitation, doesn't work for parallel writing. If not set data is not compressed.
- (boolean) **indexed_output** : if set to **true**, only not masked value are output.

+ Field time integration

- At each time step , data field are exposed from model (`xios_send_field`)
- Data are extracted according to the grid definition
- Time integration can be performed on incoming flux
- The time integration period is fixed by file output frequency (`output_freq` attribute)
- (string) `operation` attribute : time operation applied on incoming flux
 - `once` : data are used one time (first time)
 - `instant` : instant data values will be used
 - `maximum` : retains maximum data values over the integration period
 - `minimum` : retains minimum data values
 - `average` : make a time average over the period
 - `cumulate` : cumulate data over the period
- Example : each day, output the time average and instant values of "temp" field

```
<file name="output" freq_output="1d">  
  <field field_ref="temp" name="temp_average" operation="average"/>  
  <field field_ref="temp" name="temp_instant" operation="instant"/>  
</file>
```

+ Time sampling management

- Some field are not computed every time step
- (duration) `freq_op` attribute: field will be extract from model at "`freq_op`" frequency
- (duration) `freq_offset` attribute: time offset before extracting the field at "`freq_op`" frequency
- Strongly advised to set `freq_op` and `freq_offset` as a multiple of time step

- Example : for making a daily averaging, get "`temp`" value every 10 time step. The first value extracted will be at 2nd time step.

```
<file name="output" freq_output="1d">  
  <field field_ref="temp" operation="average" freq_op="10ts" freq_offset="1ts"/>  
</file>
```

+ Undefined values and time operation

- Undefined values must not participate to time integration operation
 - Set `default_value` attribute as the undefined value (missing value)
 - (boolean) `detect_missing_value` : for the current time step, all field value equal to `default_value` (undefined value) will not be taking into account to perform the time integration (`average`, `minimum`, `maximum`, `cumulate`)
- Very time CPU consuming since each value of the mesh must be tested independently

Output files : the file element <file/>

✚ Defining fields to be written

- File elements can contains field elements or group field elements
- All listed field elements will be candidate to be output
- (string) `field_group_ref` attribute: fields included in the referred field group will be included in file

```

<field_definition>
  <field_group id="fields_3d" grid_ref="grid_3d"/>
    <field id="temp" >
    <field id="precip" >
  </field_group>
  <field id="pressure" domain_ref="domain_2d"/>
</field_definition>

<file_definition>
  <file name="daily_output" freq_output="1d">
    <field field_group_ref="fields_3d" operation="average"/>
    <field_group operation="instant"/>
      <field field_ref="temp" name="temp_inst" />
      <field field_ref="pressure" name="pressure_inst" />
    </field_group>
    <field field_ref="pressure" operation="average" />
  </file>
</file_definition>

```

- Variables output as average :
 - ♦ temp
 - ♦ precip
 - ♦ pressure
- Variables output as instant
 - ♦ temp_inst
 - ♦ pressure_inst

✚ Enabling /disabling field output

- Field can be enabled/disabled individually
 - ✚ (bool) `enabled` field attribute
- Enable/disable with level output
 - ✚ (integer) `output_level` file attribute : set level of output
 - ✚ (integer) `level` field attribute : if `level` > `output_level`, field is disabled
- Enable/disable all fields
 - ✚ (boolean) `enabled` file attribute : if set to `false`, all fields are disabled
- Files with all fields disabled will not be output

✚ File format

- For now file output format is only `NETCDF`
 - ✚ `Grib2` and `HDF5` output format will be considered in future
- Can choose between parallel write into a single file or multiple file sequential output (1 file by xios server)
 - ✚ (string) `type` attribute : select output mode "`one_file`" / "`multiple_file`"
 - ✚ For "`multiple_file`" mode, files are suffixed with xios servers ranks
- Can choose between `netcdf4` et `netcdf4 classical` format
 - ✚ (string) `format` attribute : "`netcdf4`" for `netcdf4/hdf5` or "`netcdf4_classical`" for historical `netcdf3` format
 - ✚ In "`single_file`" mode, use `hdf5 parallel` for `netcdf4` format and `pnetcdf` for classical format.
 - ✚ Sequential `netcdf` library can be used in `multiple_file` mode
- Data can be compressed : only available with `netcdf4` format (`hdf5`) in sequential write (`multiple_file`)
 - ✚ (integer) `compression_level` attribute : compression level (0-9), can be fix individually with field attribute

Setting parameters : the variable element `<variable/>`

- Variable are used to define parameters
- Variable can be set or query from model
 - Could replace Fortran `namelist` or IPSL `run.def` files
- Used internally by XIOS (xios context) to define it own parameterization

+ Attributes

- (string) `name` : name of the attribute (optional)
- (string) `type` : type of the variable (optional)
 - `"bool"`, `"int16"`, `"int"`, `"int32"`, `"int64"`, `"float"`, `"double"`, `"string"`

+ Setting variable values from XML

- Values are defined in the content section

```
<variable_definition">
  <variable id="int_var" type="int"/> 10 </var>
  <variable id="string_var" type="string">a string variable</variable>
</file>
```

+ Setting or query value from model

- Set variable : `CALL xios_setvar('var_id', variable)`
- Get variable : `ierr = xios_getvar('var_id', variable)`
 - Return `true` if 'var_id' is defined and second argument contains the read value
 - return `false` if 'var_id' is not defined and second argument value is unchanged

```
<variable_definition">
  <variable id="int_var" type="int"/> 10 </var>
  <variable id="string_var" type="string">a string variable</variable>
</file>

-- from file --

USE xios
...
INTEGER :: int_var
CHARACTER(LEN=256) :: string_var
LOGICAL :: ierr

ierr=xios_getvar('int_var',intvar)
CALL xios_setvar('int_var',intvar+2)
ierr=xios_getvar('int_var',intvar)           ! -> int_var=12
ierr=xios_getvar('string_var',string_var)   ! -> string_var="a string variable"
```

✚ File structure

- XIOS respect CF convention as much as possible
- One time record (unlimited dimension) by file
 - (duration) `output_freq` attribute : define the output frequency and the time axis
 - `time_counter` dimension and axis are written conforming to CF convention
- Can mixt instant and average time operation
 - Axis `time_instant` or `time_centred` may be written with the associated bounds
- Fields of different grids can be mixt in same file
 - Longitude, latitude and verticals axis are automatically written with the associate metadata following CF convention
 - Axis boundaries will be also written if available
- Some fields attributes (`standard_name`, `long_name`, `unit`,...) will be output as field metadata

- Example of netcdf file output with XIOS

```
netcdf output_atmosphere_2D_HR {
dimensions:
    axis_nbounds = 2 ;
    lon = 200 ;
    lat = 200 ;
    time_counter = UNLIMITED ; // (30 currently)
variables:
    float lat(lat) ;
        lat:axis = "Y" ;
        lat:standard_name = "latitude" ;
        lat:long_name = "Latitude" ;
        lat:units = "degrees north" ;
        lat:nav_model = "domain_atm_HR" ;
    float lon(lon) ;
        lon:axis = "X" ;
        lon:standard_name = "longitude" ;
        lon:long_name = "Longitude" ;
        lon:units = "degrees east" ;
        lon:nav_model = "domain_atm_HR" ;
    float tsol(time_counter, lat, lon) ;
        tsol:long_name = "Surface Temperature" ;
        tsol:online_operation = "average" ;
        tsol:interval_operation = "3600 s" ;
        tsol:interval_write = "1 d" ;
        tsol:cell_methods = "time: mean (interval: 3600 s)" ;
        tsol:coordinates = "time centered" ;
    double time_centered(time_counter) ;
        time_centered:standard_name = "time" ;
        time_centered:long_name = "Time axis" ;
        time_centered:calendar = "gregorian" ;
        time_centered:units = "seconds since 1999-01-01 15:00:00" ;
        time_centered:time_origin = "1999-01-01 15:00:00" ;
        time_centered:bounds = "time centered bounds" ;
    double time_centered_bounds(time_counter, axis_nbounds) ;
    double time_counter(time_counter) ;
        time_counter:axis = "T" ;
        time_counter:standard_name = "time" ;
        time_counter:long_name = "Time axis" ;
        time_counter:calendar = "gregorian" ;
        time_counter:units = "seconds since 1999-01-01 15:00:00" ;
        time_counter:time_origin = "1999-01-01 15:00:00" ;
        time_counter:bounds = "time_counter bounds" ;
    double time_counter_bounds(time_counter, axis_nbounds) ;

// global attributes:
    :name = "output atmosphere 2D_HR" ;
    :description = "Created by xios" ;
    :title = "Created by xios" ;
    :Conventions = "CF-1.5" ;
    :production = "An IPSL model" ;
    :timeStamp = "2015-Dec-14 15:20:26 CET" ;
}
```


+ Adding specific metadata

- Using variable element `<variable/>`
- Variable file child will be output as a global netcdf file attribute
- Variable field child will be output as a netcdf variable attribute
- Example :

```
<file name="daily_output" freq_output="1d">
  <field field_ref="pressure" operation="average" />
    <variable name="int_attr" type="int"> 10 </variable>
    <variable name="double_attr" type="double"> 3.141592654 </variable>
  </field>
  <variable name="global_attribute" type="string"> A global file attribute </variable>
</file>
```

+ Flushing files

- File can be flushed periodically in order to force data in cache to be written
- (duration) `sync_freq` file attribute : flush file at `sync_freq` period

+ Appending data to an existing file

- When restart models, field data can be appended to a previous xios output files
- (boolean) `append` attribute : if set to `true` and if file is present, data will be appended
 - Otherwise a new file will be created
 - Default is creating a new file (`append=false`)

+ Splitting files

- In order to avoid biggest file, file can be split periodically
- File will suffixed with start date and end date period
- (duration) `split_freq` : split file at `split_freq` period
- Can be combine with append mode

+ Generating time series (CMIP requirement)

- Fields included into a single file may be automatically spread into individual files
- One field by file, file name based on field name
 - (string) `ts_prefix` file attribute : prefix for time series files
 - (bool) `ts_enabled` field attribute : is set to true, field is candidate to be output as time series
 - (duration) `ts_split_freq` field attribute: individual field split frequency (default is file splitting frequency)
- (string) `timeseries` file attribute (`none / only / both / exclusive`) : activate time series output
 - `none` : standard output, no time series
 - `only` : only field with `ts_enabled="true"` will be output as time series and no other output
 - `both` : timeseries + full file
 - `exclusive` : field with `ts_enabled="true"` will be output as time series, the other field in a single file

+ Reading data from file

- Very new XIOS 2 functionalities
 - Specifications and support will be improved in closed future
- (string) **mode** attribute ("read" / "write") : if set to read, file will be an input
- Each time record will be read at every **freq_output** frequency
- Value can be get from models at the corresponding time step using :
CALL **xios_rcv_field**("field_id", field)
- First time record will sent to model at time step 0 (before time loop).
- Except using **freq_offset** field attribute
 - Exemple : **freq_offset="1ts"** : first record will be read at first time step and not 0

```
<file name="daily_output" freq_output="1ts" mode="read" >  
  <field id="temp" operation="instant" freq_offset="1ts" grid_ref="grid_3d"/>  
</file>
```

```
-- From model ---
```

```
DO ts=1,n  
  CALL xios_update_timestep(ts)  
  CALL xios_rcv_field("temp",temp)  
ENDDO
```

- Field with no time record will be read only once

Why Workflow ?

- Fields are exposed from model at each time step
 - internally represent data flux assigned to a timestamp
- Each data flux can be connected to one or more filters
- Filters are connected to one or more input flux and generate a new flux on output
- All filters can be chained together to achieve complex treatment
- All filters are all parallel and scalable
- XML file describe a full graph of parallel tasks

+ Workflow entry point

- Input flux can be a field sent from model (`xios_send_field`)
- Input flux can be a field read from an input file

+ Workflow end point

- Output flux can be sent to servers and written to file
- Output flux can be read from model (`xios_rcv_field`)
 - (boolean) `read_access` field attribute : field read from models must set `read_access="true"`
 - Field directly read from file have automatically `read_access="true"`

```

<field id="precip" grid_ref="grid_3d"/>
<field id="pressure" field_ref="p" read_access="true" unit="Pa" / >
<field id="precip_read" field_ref="precip" read_access="true" />

<file name="daily_output" freq_output="1ts">
  <field id="temp" operation="instant" grid_ref="grid_3d"/>
  <field id="p" operation="instant" domain_ref="domain_2d"/>
</file>

-- From model ---

DO ts=1,n
  CALL xios_update_timestep(ts)
  CALL xios_send_field("precip",precip)
  CALL xios_rcv_field("temp",temp)
  CALL xios_rcv_field("pressure",pressure)
  CALL xios_rcv_field("precip_read",precip_read) ! Now precip_read==precip
ENDDO

```

+ field_ref attribute : duplicate flux from the referenced field

- For each reference to field, a new flux is created by duplicating source flux

- Also, make XML inheritance

Defining filters and transformations

✚ Actually 3 kind of filters

- Arithmetic filters : combine flux together
- Time integration filters : integrate flux over a period
- Spatial filters : modify the geometry of the incoming flux

✚ Arithmetic filters

- Arithmetic filter can combine different flux of same timestamp with arithmetic operator or function
- All incoming flux must be on the same grid
 - ✚ Perform same operations for each grid point
- Arithmetic filter are defined in the content section of a field element
- Computed flux value will replace actual flux, even if coming from reference

```
<field id="temp" unit="°C" grid_ref="grid_3d"/>  
<field id="temp_K" unit="°K" field_ref="temp"> temp-273.15 </field>
```

- Specific "this" (auto-reference) keyword representing the incoming flux of the current field

```
<field id="temp" unit="°K" grid_ref="grid_3d"> this-273.15 </field>
```

- Arithmetic filters can be easily chained,
 - Computed flux can be reused

$$C = \frac{A + B}{A * B}$$

$$D = \frac{e^{-C*D}}{3}$$

```
<field id="A" />
<field id="B" />
<field id="C" > (A + B) / (A*B) </field>
<field id="D" > exp(-C*this) / 3 </field>
```

Time integration filters

- Time filters of are specified with the "operation" field attribute
 - Possible value : "once", "instant", "maximum", "minimum", "average", "cumulate"
 - A new flux is generated at the end of the time integration period
- Time filter is enabled only if :
 - Field is included into a file
 - output_freq define the period over the time integration is done
 - Generated flux is the sent to servers to be written

- Flux will be reused by another field after time integration
 - The @ operator : means that time integration is performed over the flux
 - The time integration period is given by value of `freq_op` attribute of new flux

```
<field id="temp" operation="average" />
<field id="temp_ave" freq_op="1d"/> @temp </field>
```

- New flux "temp_ave" is created every day (`freq_op="1day"`) by time averaging of "temp" flux

✚ Chaining time filters

- Using the @ operator
- Example : compute and output the monthly average of the daily maximum and minimum of temperature and the monthly maximum and minimum of the daily temperature average

```
<field id="temp" operation="average"/>
<field id="temp_min" field_ref="temp" operation="minimum" />
<field id="temp_max" field_ref="temp" operation="maximum" />

<file name="monthly_output" freq_output="1mo" />
  <field name="ave_daily_min" operation="average" freq_op="1d"> @temp_min </field>
  <field name="ave_daily_max" operation="average" freq_op="1d"> @temp_max </field>
  <field name="min_daily_ave" operation="minimum" freq_op="1d"> @temp </field>
  <field name="max_daily_ave" operation="maximum" freq_op="1d"> @temp </field>
</file>

  --from model--
CALL xios_send_field("temp", temp)
```

+ Chaining and combine time filters and arithmetic's filters

- Compute the time variance of a temperature field $\sigma \approx \sqrt{\langle T^2 \rangle - \langle T \rangle^2}$

```
<field id="temp" operation="average"/>
<field id="temp2" field_ref="temp" /> temp*temp </field>

<file name="monthly_output" freq_output="1mo" />
  <field name="sigma_T" operation="instant" freq_op="1mo"> sqrt(@temp2-pow(@temp,2)) </field>
</file>

  --from model--
CALL xios_send_field("temp",temp)
```

Spatial filters

- Spatial filters may change the geometry, dimensionality and the parallelism data distribution of a flux
- Algorithms must parallel and scalable in order to perform the flux transformation on whole allocated parallel resources of a simulation
- Difficult to develop, such features are still experimental in XIOS 2
- Actually, limited number of filters, more such parallel filters will be develop in future

✚ Using spatial filter

- Spatial filters are enabled when the grid of a referenced field is different of the current grid field

- ✚ No spatial filter enabled (same grid ref)

```
<field id="temp" grid_ref="grid_regular"/>  
<field id="new_temp" field_ref="temp" grid_ref="grid_regular" />
```

- ✚ Try to enabled spatial filter (different grid ref)

```
<field id="temp" grid_ref="grid_regular"/>  
<field id="new_temp" field_ref="temp" grid_ref="grid_unstruct" />
```

- If grid are not matching exactly, try to find a way to transform source grid into target grid
 - ✚ If not possible an error is generated
 - ✚ Otherwise filter will be used

- To find which filters to activate, a matching is done between domain and axis composing the grid.
 - An exact matching between element do not activate filter
 - If not matching, see if it is possible to transform the source element domain or axis into target element with a transformation.
 - Otherwise an error is generated

```
<field id="temp" grid_ref="grid_regular"/>
<field id="new_temp" field_ref="temp" grid_ref="grid_unstruct" />

<axis id="vert_axis" n_glo="100" />
<domain id="regular" ni_glo="360" nj_glo="180" type="rectilinear" />
<domain id="unstruct" ni_glo="10000" type="unstructured" />

<grid id="grid_regular">
  <domain domain_ref="regular">
    <axis axis_ref="vert_axis" >
  </grid>

<grid id="grid_unstructured">
  <domain domain_ref="unstructured">
    <interpolate_domain/>
  <domain/>
  <axis axis_ref="vert_axis" >
</grid>
```

- Implement interpolation filter between "regular" domain and "unstruct" domain, no filter implemented between axis

- More than one filter can be implemented in same transformation

```
<axis id="vert_src" n_glo="100" />
<axis id="vert_dst" n_glo="50" />

<domain id="regular" ni_glo="360" nj_glo="180" type="rectilinear" />
<domain id="unstruct" ni_glo="10000" type="unstructured" />

<grid id="grid_regular">
  <domain domain_ref="regular"/>
  <axis axis_ref="vert_src" />
</grid>

<grid id="grid_unstructured">
  <domain domain_ref="unstructured">
    <interpolate_domain/>
  </domain>
  <axis axis_ref="vert_dst">
    <interpolate_axis/>
  </axis>
</grid>
```

- Domain interpolation will be perform first "regular" -> "unstructured"
- Axis interpolation will be perform in 2nd time "vert_src" -> "vert_dst"

Spatial filters actually developed

+ Zooming filters

- ◊ Extract sub-part of data
- ◊ Zoom on axis
 - `zoom_axis` transform
 - (integer) `begin` attribute : global beginning index of the zoom
 - (integer) `n` attribute : global size of the zoom
- ◊ Zoom on domains
 - `zoom_domain` transform
 - (integer) `ibegin` attribute : global beginning index of 1st dimension of the zoom
 - (integer) `ni` attribute : global beginning index of 1st dimension of the zoom
 - (integer) `jbegin` attribute : global beginning index of 2nd dimension of the zoom (for rectilinear or curvilinear)
 - (integer) `nj` attribute : global beginning index of 2nd dimension of the zoom (for rectilinear or curvilinear)

```
<field id="temp" grid_ref="grid_regular"/>
<field id="temp_zoomed" field_ref="temp" grid_ref="grid_zoom" />

<axis id="vert_src" n="100" />
<domain id="regular" ni_glo="360" nj_glo="180" type="rectilinear" />

<grid id="grid_regular">
  <domain domain_ref="regular"/>
  <axis axis_ref="vert_src" />
</grid>

<grid id="grid_zoom">
  <domain domain_ref="regular">
    <zoom_domain ibegin="20" ni="50" jbegin="100" nj="60" />
  </domain/>
  <axis axis_ref="vert_src">
    <zoom_axis begin="30" n="40"/>
  </axis>
</grid>
```

- ▶ Zoom of global size (50, 60, 40) starting at indices (20, 100, 30)
- ▶ Only this part will be output to files

+ Inverse axis data and coordinates

- `inverse_axis` transformation

+ Interpolate/remap axis and domain

- Axis interpolation
 - Actually only polynomial interpolation
- `interpolate_axis` transformation
 - (integer) `order` attribute : set the order of the polynomial interpolation

➤ Ex:

```
<axis n_glo="100">  
  <interpolate_axis order="2"/>  
</axis>
```

- Domain interpolation
 - Perform interpolation between any kind of domain
 - Compute weight on the fly and in parallel at xios closing definition step
 - Interpolation is done on parallel on the incoming distributed flux
 - Current algorithm is only conservative remapping of 1st or 2nd order
- `interpolate_domain` transformation
 - (integer) `order` attribute : set the order of the conservative interpolation (1 or 2)

➤ Ex :

```
<domain ni_glo="10000" type="unstructured">  
  <interpolate_domain order="2"/>  
</domain>
```

+ Generating missing attribute on regular rectilinear grid

- Still experimental
- Generate automatically parallel distribution
- Generate automatically longitude and latitude values
- ◊ **generate_rectilinear_domain** transform
 - (double) **lon_start**, **lon_end**, **lat_start**, **lat_end** attr: in north degrees, nothing means global grid
 - (double) **bounds_lon_start**, **bounds_lon_end**, **bounds_lat_start**, **bounds_lat_end** attr : for boundaries version
 - Useful to perform automatic interpolation on regular grid

```

<domain id="unstruct" ni_glo="10000" type="unstructured" />
<domain id="regular" ni_glo="360" nj_glo="180" type="rectilinear" />

<grid id="grid_unstructured">
  <domain domain_ref="unstruct" />
</grid>

<grid id="grid_regular">
  <domain domain_ref="regular"/>
  <generate_rectilinear_domain/> <!-- Create automatically 1° resolution regular domain -->
  <interpolate_domain/> <!-- and remap -->
  <domain/>
</grid>

<field id="temp_unst" grid_ref="unstruct"/>
<field id="temp_reg" field_ref="temp_unst" grid_ref="grid_regular"/>

```

+ Chaining spatial transformation

- Chaining can be easily achieved by referencing intermediate field
 - Ex : interpolate unstructured grid to regular and then make a zoom

```
<field id="temp_unstr"           grid_ref="grid_unstruct"/>
<field id="temp_reg"           field_ref="temp_unstr"   grid_ref="grid_regular"/>
<field id="temp_reg_zoom"      field_ref="temp_reg"    grid_ref="grid_regular_zoom"/>
```

- To avoid intermediate field definition, use `grid_path` attribute
 - (string) `grid_path` attribute : define the list of intermediate grid

```
<field id="temp_unstr"           grid_ref="grid_unstruct"/>
<field id="temp_reg_zoom"      field_ref="temp_unstr"   grid_path="grid_regular"   grid_ref="grid_regular_zoom"/>
```

- Other possibilities is to chain transformation in same domain or axis transformation definition

```
<field id="temp_unstr" domain_ref="unstructured" />
<field id="temp_reg_zoom" field_ref="temp_unstr" domain_ref="regular_zoom"/>

<domain id="unstructured"   n_glo="10000" type="unstructured" />

<domain id="regular_zoom"  ni_glo="360" nj_glo="180" type="rectilinear">
  <generate_rectilinear_domain/>
  <interpolate_domain/>
  <zoom_domain ibegin="20" ni="50" jbegin="100" nj="60" />
</domain>
```

```
SUBROUTINE client(rank,size)
  USE xios
  IMPLICIT NONE
  INTEGER :: rank, size
  TYPE(xios_time)      :: dtime
  DOUBLE PRECISION,ALLOCATABLE :: lon(:,,:),lat(:,,:),a_field(:,:)
  ! other variable declaration and initialisation .....

! XIOS initialization
  CALL xios_initialize("client", return_comm=comm)
  CALL xios_context_initialize("hello_word",comm)
! Complete horizontal domain definition
  CALL xios_set_domain_attr("horizontal_domain",ibegin=ibegin,ni=ni,jbegin=jbegin, nj=nj)
  CALL xios_set_domain_attr("horizontal_domain ",lonvalue_2d=lon, latvalue_2d=lat)
! Setting time step
  dtime%second=3600
  CALL xios_set_timestep(dtime)
! Closing definition
  CALL xios_close_context_definition()
! Entering time loop
  DO ts=1,96
    CALL xios_update_calendar(ts)
    CALL xios_send_field("a_field",a_field)
  ENDDO
! XIOS finalization
  CALL xios_context_finalize()
  CALL xios_finalize()
END SUBROUTINE client
```

Fortran structure to be XIOS compliant

- For an exhaustive description of XIOS Fortran API : see xios reference guide

+ XIOS Initialization

- XML files are parsed at initialization
- CALL `xios_initialize("code_id", return_comm=communicator)`
 - "code_id" must be the same for all process rank of same model
 - XIOS split the `MPI_COMM_WORLD` communicator between clients and servers and return the split one for client side

+ Context initialization

- CALL `xios_context_initialize("context_id", communicator)`
 - "context_id" : id of the context to bind with context defined in XML file
 - `communicator` : MPI communicator associated to the context
 - Must be the same or a sub communicator of which returned at xios initialization
- Context initialization can be done at any time
- Several different context can be initialized during same run
- All xios fortran call are collective for the related current context MPI communicator

+ Switching to a context

- CALL `set_current_context("context_id")`
 - All behind xios fortran call will be related to context "context_id"

+ Complete the XML database definition

- Fix missing attribute
 - Some attribute values are known only at run time
- All attribute can be fixed use the fortran API
 - CALL `xios_set_element_attr("element_id", attr1=attr1_value, attr2=attr2_value, ...)`
- New child element can be added
 - All XML tree can be created from fortran interface
 - Ex : adding "temp" field element to "field_definition" group

```
CALL xios_get_handle("field_definition", field_group_handle)
CALL xios_add_child(field_group_handle, field_handle, id="temp")
```

+ Setting time step and other calendar specific attributes

+ Closing context definition

- CALL `xios_close_context_definition`
- Context data base is analyzed and processed
- Any modification behind this point would not be taken into account and unexpected results may occur

+ Entering time loop

- When entering a new time step, XIOS must be informed
- CALL `xios_update_timestep(ts)`
 - `ts` : timestep number
- Time step must begin to 1
- Time step 0 refers to part between context closure and first time step update
 - Only received field request can be done at time step 0
 - Sent field request are not taking into account at time step 0
- Data can be exposed during a time step
 - CALL `xios_send_field("field_id", field)`
 - CALL `xios_rcv_field("field_id", field)`
 - Sent data field would create a new flux tagged with timestamp related to the time step
 - Data can be received only if the outgoing flux have the same timestamp that the related time step

+ Finalize context

- All opened context must be finalized after the end of time loop
- CALL `xios_context_finalize`

+ Finalize xios

- After finalizing all opened context, xios must be finalized, servers are informed, files are properly closed and performance report is generated
- CALL `xios_finalize`

Performance

- IO become a big bottleneck in parallel computing up to $O(10000)$ cores
 - Often, data are gathered to one master process which write file
 - Ok if done just for initialization or finalize but memory problem may occur
 - Big impact on computing performance
- One file by process ?
 - Good way to achieve moderate scalability but :
 - Depending of the file system, performance may breaking down when attempt to write simultaneously thousand of files
 - Files need to be rebuilt into a single file in order to be analyzed :
 - Rebuilt may take a longer time than the simulations

- ◊ Using parallel IO ?
 - ✦ Best way to achieve scalable IO without rebuild file
 - ✦ But difficult to aggregate a lot of I/O bandwidth with a big number of writing processes
 - ✦ Parallel IO are very less scalable than models due to hardware restriction (pricy and not took into account for performance evaluation)
 - ✦ Impact on the computing performances.

- ◊ Using asynchronous parallel IO ?
 - ✦ Good way to overlap IO by computing
 - ✦ MPI/IO : difficult to manage, load balancing problem...
 - ✦ High level library (HDF5, netcdf...) generally don't implement asynchronous IO.

- ◊ I/O performances are very system dependent
 - ✦ Example : Curie Tier 0 computer with LUSTRE file system
 - ✦ 150 GB/s theoretical capability
 - ✦ Optimally tuned MPI-IO parallel benchmark : 10 GB/s
 - ✦ HDF5 layer ~ 5GB/s
 - ✦ NETCDF4-HDF5 layer ~ 4GB/s

- Achieving good parallel IO performance is not so easy :
 - A lot of recipes to avoid very bad performance
 - Example with netcdf4, trying to perform naïve parallel IO

-Multiple file on 16 CPUs : 1 file by process = 16 files

-Single file on 16 CPUs : 1 rebuilt file (collective access or independent access)

XIOS servers

Pool of process dedicated to parallel I/O

✚ XIOS : a software Burst Buffer ?

- Data are written all along the simulation
- Smoothing I/O peaks
- Constant I/O flow to file system
- Overlap I/O by computation

Complex and fully asynchronous protocol

- One way to send data from clients to servers
- One way to receive data from servers to clients

✚ Same pools of I/O servers used in coupled model

✚ Different data distribution between client and servers

✚ Data are sent asynchronously at writing time

- Use only MPI point to point asynchronous communication : MPI_Issend, MPI_Irecv, MPI_Test, MPI_Probe...
- No synchronization point between clients and server, and between servers
- No latency cost, communications are overlapped by computation
- Writing is also overlapped by computation

✚ Data are received asynchronously with prefetching (by advance) on client side

+ Large usage of buffers

- Smoothing I/O peaks

+ Client Side : double buffers

- Outgoing message in transfer
- Bufferization of the incoming flow

+ Server Side : circular buffer

- Received request are processed
- In same time than receiving request from client

Overlapping data transfer and I/O by computing

+ Understand and analyze XIOS servers performance

- Build a toy model
- Field is sent and written at each time step
- Some extra working time is simulate by a waiting call

```
! Entering time loop
DO ts=1000
  CALL xios_update_calendar(ts)
  CALL xios_send_field("field", field)
  CALL wait_us(80000)    ! Wait 80 milliseconds to simulate some works
ENDDO
```

- Look at parallel vampir trace
 - Green : application time
 - Red : MPI function time
 - Orange : server working time
 - Brown : client waiting for free buffer and blocking
- Make experiments by decreasing working time compared to I/O output

Performance report

- Report is generated at XIOS finalization

Client side : xios_client_00.out

```
-> report : Performance report : total time spent for XIOS : 32.3497 s
-> report : Performance report : time spent for waiting free buffer : 1.1336 s
-> report : Performance report : Ratio : 3.50421 %
-> report : Performance report : This ratio must be close to zero. Otherwise it may be useful
to increase buffer size or numbers of server
```

Server side : xios_server_00.out

```
-> report : Performance report : Time spent for XIOS : 51.0071
-> report : Performance report : Time spent in processing events : 21.5263
-> report : Performance report : Ratio : 42.2026%
```

+ Client side : Time spent for waiting free buffer is small compare to total time

- Every thing is OK, no impact of I/O on computing time

+ Client side : Time spent for waiting free buffer is not insignificant

- Server side : if ratio (total time / time for process event) is close to 100%
 - ▶ I/O throughput is not enough fast to maintains asynchronism
 - ▶ Add more servers
- Servers side : if ratio is much less than 100% (60-80%)
 - ▶ Servers are not overloaded but cannot absorb and smooth I/O peaks
 - ▶ Buffer are to small and need to be increased

+ Placing XIOS servers in parallel partition

- Strongly hardware dependent
- But generally better to spread servers on different computing nodes

+ Attached mode

- To make development easier XIOS provide an "attach" mode
 - Don't need to launch xios servers executable
 - XIOS act only as a library
- Each client is itself a server for the other clients
 - Pool of servers is equal to the number of clients
- Synchronous mode only
 - Client must wait that sent data is written before continue
- "Single file" mode : all client process attempt to write parts of file
 - Bad for performance for high number of clients
- "Multiple file" mode : one file by client
 - Difficult to rebuild in post-treatment

Memory consumption

- XIOS consume memory internally to make averaging and other operations
- XIOS use large transfer buffer for asynchronous protocol
- Part of memory is all consumed by NETCDF4/HDF5
- But generally, memory consumption is scalable
 - Increasing number of clients decrease memory consumption on client side
 - Increasing number of servers decrease memory consumption on server side

+ Memory report

- Give informations about memory used by transfer buffer
- Buffer size is automatically computed
 - Can be different for each communication channel client-server couple
 - Dependent of the parallel data distribution
- For each couple client-server, 2 channels, 2 different buffers
 - 1 for sending/receiving data client -> server (I/O write)
 - 1 for sending/receiving data server -> client (I/O read)

Client side : xios_client_00.out

```
-> report : Memory report : Context <atmosphere> : client side : total memory used for buffer 2932872 bytes
-> report : Memory report : Context <atmosphere> : server side : total memory used for buffer 209733 bytes
-> report : Memory report : Minimum buffer size required : 209730 bytes
-> report : Memory report : increasing it by a factor will increase performance, depending of the volume of
data wrote in file at each time step of the file
```

Server side : xios_server_00.out

```
-> report : Memory report : Context <atmosphere_server> : client side : total memory used for buffer 209733
bytes
-> report : Memory report : Context <atmosphere_server> : server side : total memory used for buffer 1710664
bytes
```

+ Managing buffer size

- Buffer sizes are automatically computed
- User can choose between 2 behaviors (parameter `optimal_buffer_size`):
- Buffer sizes optimized for memory
 - Size adjusted to the biggest transfer
 - Minimal memory consumption for buffer
 - But loosing most part of asynchronous transfer
- Buffer sizes optimized for performance
 - Sizes are adjusted to bufferize all data between two output period
 - Fully asynchronous
- User can adjust size by itself using a multiplying factor
 - (double) `buffer_size_factor` parameter

Performance : what to expect...

+ XIOS is used on simulation with $O(10\ 000)$ cores and more...

- Ex: CINES Big Challenges 2014 : DYNAMICO 1/8° and NEMO 1/60°

+ Bench test case : NEMO 1/12°

- Gyre configuration : 4322 x 2882 x 31 : 8160 cores
- Curie supercomputer : Lustre file system : theoretical Bandwidth : 150 GB/s (announced)
- Practical Bandwidth : NETCDF4/HDF5 file format : parallel write access on a single file (tuned): ~ 5 GB / s
- 6 days simulation (2880 time steps) ~ 300 s run s

+ 6-hours frequency output files (~200 GB of data produced, 4 files)

- 8160 NEMO, 32 XIOS servers
- +5% penalty for I/O (comparable to OS jittering)

+ Extreme test case : hourly output files (~1.1 TB of data produced, 4 files)

- 8160 NEMO, 128 XIOS servers (1.5 % resources for I/O)
- 15-20% penalty for I/O
- 3.6 GB/s I/O flux continuously
- **Generated data amount : ~300 TB by day, ~10 PB by month**

+ XIOS context is used for parameterization

- Specific XIOS context in XML file
- Used only for reading variable value
- Actually, all parameters are optional, just override default value

```
<context id="xios">
  <variable_definition>

    <variable id="optimal_buffer_size" type="string">performance</variable>
    <variable id="buffer_size_factor" type="double">1.0</variable>
    <variable id="min_buffer_size" type="int">100000</variable>
    <variable id="using_server" type="bool">>false</variable>
    <variable id="using_oasis" type="bool">>false</variable>
    <variable id="info_level" type="int">50</variable>
    <variable id="print_file" type="bool">>true</variable>

  </variable_definition>
</context>
```

- (string) `optimal_buffer_size` : specify buffer sizing behavior (default : "performance")
 - "performance" or "memory"

- ◊ (double) `buffer_size_factor` : multiplying the computed buffer size by this factor
 - Use with caution
- ◊ (integer) `min_buffer_size` : fix the minimum size of buffers
 - Use only in case of bad computed size
 - Can help to workaround an unexpected problem
- ◊ (boolean) `using_server`: specify "server mode" or "attached mode"
 - XIOS try to determine itself the chosen mode by analyzing MPI communicator
 - Usefull only for coupled model configuration
- ◊ (boolean) `using_oasis` : used when interfaced with oasis (expert mode), (`default=false`)
- ◊ (integer) `info_level`: level of xios information output (0-100), 0 nothing, 100 full, (`default=0`)
- ◊ (boolean) `print_file` : if true, xios standard output and error are redirected in files indexed by process rank, (`default=false`)